

Highlighting The Significance Of Politics And Ethics And Alain Badiou

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Abstract

It is widely acknowledged that Alain Badiou, a French philosopher, is among the most influential thinkers in the field of modern philosophy. It is particularly since the close of the 20th century that his impact on the field of philosophy has acquired a significant deal of momentum. The novel and radical insights that Badiou gives in fields like as politics, ethics, mathematics, and ontology are an important part of the reason why his philosophy is so well-known. He constructs intellectual bridges between many thinkers, including Plato, Kant, Hegel, Marx, Mao, Lacan, and Deleuze, via the works that he has produced. He does this by bringing together diverse schools of thought including these. the purpose of this study is to investigate the connection between politics and ethics, which Alain Badiou considers to be the fundamental need for a human being to live a human life. The purpose of this research is to examine the distinction between "what is" and "what should be" and to bring to light the fact that this distinction serves as the point of departure for the inquiry process. In a time when human connections are growing more complicated, the purpose of this article is to present Badiou's philosophical beliefs and viewpoint by highlighting the significance of politics and ethics. Badiou's philosophical writings are notable for the bridges he builds with many thought sources, including Plato, Kant, Hegel, Marx, Mao, Lacan, and Deleuze. These bridges are what really set his works apart.

Keywords: *Alain Badiou, Politics, Ethics, Philosophy And Politics, Political And Ethical Challenges*

Introduction

The singularity of Badiou's method is further shown by the fact that he is able to blend concepts from a variety of domains and provide connections between philosophy and a wide range of disciplines. The objective of this work is to conduct a more in-depth investigation of Badiou's

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philosophical perspectives and multidisciplinary approach. Within the scope of this investigation, Badiou's philosophical perspectives are analogous to the connection that exists between politics and ethics. These inquiries were carried out with the purpose of gaining an understanding of the contemporary political and ethical challenges.

Indeed, Badiou, the political arena is the only place where individuals may fulfill their ethical beliefs. It is remarkable, however, that political acts and ethical beliefs are incompatible with one another in today's contemporary world. In spite of the fact that some nations justify their political and military interventions on the basis of ethical considerations, it is said that these interventions are more closely connected to economic concerns.

Furthermore, Badiou underlined the difference between morality and ethics in his writings. The term "moral" should be used to describe individuals' own views and actions, but people more often use the term "ethical" to describe them. It is because of this misconception that the substance of the idea of ethics gets obscured.

Aim

In addition, the essay highlights the fact that multiculturalism makes it more difficult to comprehend ethics, and that ideas like human rights impede the formation of a comprehensive comprehension of ethics. These kinds of methods, according to Badiou, have the effect of putting individuals in the position of victims and preventing them from properly comprehending ethics. Badiou contends that in order for individuals to be able to achieve ethical principles in politics, it is necessary for these two sectors to be compatible with one another. The fact that this compatibility cannot be attained, however, is shown by a number of existing difficulties.

Methodology

On the other hand, Western capitalism and parliamentary democracy are being imposed as a

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global paradigm in today's world, as stated by Badiou. This imposition is the result of a conservative way of thinking that leads to politics being sterile when it is implemented. This conservative way of thinking not only makes politics vulnerable to the corrupting and destructive force of capital, but it also uses the ideas of politics and ethics as a means of exerting control over the values that are associated with its own sovereignty. On the other hand, according to Badiou, the instrumentalization of these two categories that are unique to humans results in the creation of just one thing for humans, and that is nihilism.

Literature Review

People are relegated to a predetermined necessity as a result of the silence of politics and ethics in response to this emptiness. Within this essential domain, there is a collection of well-established information and beliefs that are completely devoid of any reality whatsoever. Consequently, the socializing of the human animal, which is characterized by the pursuit of its own interests, is restricted to the domain of established knowledge and ideas. In other words, existing knowledge and ideas become the main element of all sorts of sociality and communication (Badiou , 2013c). Nevertheless, despite the fact that the domain of views extols the principles of the modern democratic society, such as freedom and equality, in reality, it is freedom and equality in the face of commercial commodities that man is confronted with. The freedom to buy is the freedom that is promised by the regime of ideas, and the guarantee of equality is that anybody who is free to purchase is legally equal to everyone else (Badiou, 2016b). In other words, the freedom that they offer is the freedom to purchase. Badiou is fundamentally opposed to the concept of a "universalizable ethics" due to the fact that the current understanding of politics and ethics has become subservient to the coercive power of capital. On the one hand, the realm of opinions presents the so-called values of capitalist parliamentary democracy to man as the best of all possible worlds. On the other hand, today's understanding of politics and ethics has become subservient to the power of capital. Badiou is opposed to the efforts to build a "universal ethics" for a number of reasons, one of which is the nature of the idea of ethics in the modern day, which is fashioned under the banner of tolerance

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for the Other and whose roots are founded on Emmanuel Levinas. According to Levinas's theses, the need for ethics, which presents itself as respect for diversity and all cultures and develops a connection with the Other, is derived from a religious foundation. This is the case because the demand for ethics establishes a relationship with the Other.

Argument

The ethics of respect and tolerance for the Other, on the other hand, have been separated from their religious foundations and converted into a fight for recognition based on identification in today's society. The term "ethical ideology" is used by Badiou to refer to these kinds of ethical systems, which are characterized by the acceptance of cultural relativism and multiculturalism and are just the right to not notice evil.

In spite of the fact that the idea of human rights include rights that have traditionally been safeguarded and acknowledged by the legal systems of nations, Badiou believes that the human rights abuses that have occurred have brought to light the problematic features of the methodologies that are now being used. In his analysis, Badiou considers human rights to be a distinct ethical problem. When people are seen only as helpless and passive living things, however, this perspective contributes to the propagation of an ideology that extols the concept that human rights are predicated on the victim identity of the subject population. This approach, according to Badiou, transforms human rights ethics into an ideology that does not take into consideration people in any meaningful way. Even if Badiou is of the opinion that every single human being has a distinct worth, he is opposed to the notion that Western conservatives are the only ones who can safeguard this value. As far as he is concerned, human rights always result in the victim continuing to be a victim, while the strong are always portrayed as the protector and superior. It is necessary, therefore, to conduct an evaluation of this ethical approach. Instead of focusing on the "human victim" and the "mortal, featherless bipedal" conception of humans, it is necessary to emphasize the subject that is capable of producing, manufacturing, engaging in politics, falling in love, inventing, being creative, and being

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immortal. The individual rights that are outlined in the declaration of human rights are not something that Badiou is opposed to. The notion that the basic human rights that are outlined in the Universal Declaration of Human Rights bind everyone is something that he takes issue with, as does the assertion that these rights are constrained by the consent of the people. As an additional point of view, he is of the opinion that the moral and philosophical justifications that are used to justify these rights are either insufficient or problematic. How are we able to exercise control over the validity of these rights if there is no argument that serves as the foundation for them? The failure to understand the moral and philosophical basis on which the human rights discourse is built, where the only legitimate claim is universality, and the consensus of this discourse built on Evil are based, Badiou argues, necessitates caution regarding today's human rights discourse. Badiou is among those who are opposed to the lack of sufficient data on this issue. According to Badiou, the "correct ethical person" of today is both incomplete and incorrect (Badiou, 2013c, page 32). This conclusion is based on the judgments listed above. This kind of ethical reasoning, according to him, inhibits us from being able to think about the individuality and originality of occurrences. In light of this, Badiou puts up three new basic theses that challenge the current understanding of ethics (Badiou, 2013c, page 24).

First Thesis

The ability of man to think positively and the individual truths that he is capable of reaching are the defining characteristics of man. The Immortal, according to this concept, is the animal that is the most lasting and contradictory of all the kinds of creatures. The second thesis is that in order to define evil, it is essential to reject our capacity to achieve good and our desire to exhibit a limitless attitude in this context, which is a kind of conservatism that encompasses the preservation of life. However, this is not the case in reverse. The identification of distinct occurrences in mind is the basis upon which all of mankind is built, according to the third thesis. The term "ethics" does not exist in the way that it is often understood. The ethics of procedures that include questioning the potentialities of a situation are the only ones that might be considered ethical.

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These theses provide a foundation for Badiou's critique of the current understanding of ethics and propose that our knowledge of human life, thinking, and ethics should be reviewed from a new point of view.

People, Badiou, are so different from animals that they do not think about them and have an infinite capacity for thinking. This is a significant difference. In order for people to possess this capacity for thinking, they must exhibit a fearless attitude, reject conservatism and formal morality, and refuse to accept a narrow idea of good that is imposed by societal conventions. According to Badiou (2013c), when people allow themselves to be entirely open to thought via the use of their positive thinking, they become into eternal subjects of solitary truths that they are able to achieve.

The contemporary view of ethics and human rights, on the other hand, depicts people as fragile and passive creatures, restricts them to their physical, cultural, religious, national, and ethnic identities, and supports a battle for recognition based on their identities. Badiou contends that this understanding paves the way for cultural relativism and multiculturalism, particularly in the context of an actor bearing the human rights rhetoric of the Western world. In his argument, Badiou contends that "good others" whose differences are tolerated lose their distinctions and are only accepted if they adopt established norms such as the market economy, parliamentary government, and human rights. He says this is the only condition under which they are accepted.

Badiou, the genesis of this approach may be traced back to Emmanuel Levinas and his concept of "ethical radicalism" (Turk, 2013, p. 229). The ethical perspective of Levinas has had an impact on the ethical and political vocabulary of today, and it has positioned the idea of the "Other" at the heart of the discussion. Emmanuel Levinas's idea of the Other serves as the foundation for Badiou's criticism of yet another problematic component of the contemporary ethical thinking. Therefore, according to him, the ethical thinking that exists now has really progressed quite a distance away from the notions that Levinas proposed. Within the framework of this critique, it is essential to first provide an explanation of the factors that led Levinas to prioritize ethics above ontology and to place the construction of the "I" under the authority of the Other.

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Badiou, according to Levinas's theory, the "I" transforms into an ethical subject by committing oneself to the Other. This approach serves as the foundation for the ethics of tolerance that are prevalent in today's society, which may also be referred to as the ethics of the other. Nevertheless, Badiou believes that the ethics of the other that are prevalent in today's society have misread Levinas's initial notion. In particular, the ethics of the other that are prevalent in today's society are incompatible with Levinas's ideology of the "right to difference," which he based on religious origins. This ideology encourages diversity by reducing differences, which is a key component of multiculturalism. Based on Badiou's assessment, it is evident that the original ethical message has not been comprehended, resulting in the loss of its significance (Badiou, 2013c, pp. 33-41).

Ethics and Concerning Political Ethics

Ethics is a branch of philosophy that examines the judgment of human conduct in terms of what constitutes right and wrong, as well as what constitutes good and evil. This field of study seeks to investigate the standards and principles that individuals use in order to establish what constitutes good and wrong. It is the purpose of ethics to call into question the moral obligations, values, and actions of individuals as well as social groups. A deontological theory, a teleological theory, and an adult ethical theory are the three primary categories of ethical theories. While deontology places an emphasis on the moral merits of the acts themselves, teleology places more of an emphasis on the outcomes of such activities. Contextual and situational elements are said to have a significant role in shaping ethical judgments, according to adult ethical theories. People may better comprehend their obligations to themselves, to other people, and to nature via the study of ethics, which also helps them identify their values.

When people talk about political ethics, they are referring to a discipline that investigates the ethical aspects of public life and politics. It is the responsibility of this profession to assess the ethical implications of political choices, acts taken by the government, policy-making procedures, and public policies. In the field of political ethics, themes such as social fairness,

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equality, freedom, justice, and human rights are the primary areas of attention. Within this document, the manner in which political leaders, governments, and political institutions need to behave in line with these ideals is discussed.

Political ethics also examines topics such as the use of power and authority, democracy, governance, and the function of the state, while also challenging the influence that these notions have on political choices and the faith that society places in political leaders and institutions. For the purpose of arguing that public services ought to be provided in accordance with the highest moral standards, political ethics places an emphasis on the honesty, accountability, and openness of political leaders.

A better understanding of the ethical components of people's individual and societal activities is provided by these two notions, which also provide direction for the manner in which politics ought to best serve society. In order to ensure the health and happiness of both people and society, it is essential to position ethical principles at the core of political discourse.

Politics and Ethics in Action

Politics is a process that governs the administration of societies, the allocation of resources, and the fundamental laws that govern basic social interactions. The scope of politics, on the other hand, extends beyond administration and decision-making; it also defines the manner in which the fundamental principles of societies are represented in the public domain. As a result, the connection between ethics and politics is one that is both exceedingly complicated and quite significant.

Politics, in its most fundamental sense, is the endeavor of striking a balance between the dissimilar values, requirements, and objectives of diverse parts of society. When it comes to achieving this equilibrium, politicians and others in charge of making decisions have to take ethical principles into mind. For both people and society, ethics is a tool that assists in defining the boundaries between right and evil. The application of these limits inside the public realm is the path that politics takes in order to safeguard the interests of society and justice.

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Comparatively, ethics is basically founded on ideals, but politics often calls for thinking that is both practical and strategic. It is for this reason that politicians may sometimes be required to interpret ethical principles and ideals in a flexible manner. In the case of the objective of achieving equal distribution of public resources, for instance, this is an ethical ideal; but, pragmatism and strategy may play a significant part in choosing which policies are the most successful in achieving this goal.

In the realm of ethics and politics, human rights constitute a significant intersectional issue. Human rights are the basic rights that are inherent to every single person from the moment of their birth. The actions and policies of the political system need to be able to safeguard these rights. When it comes to politics, human rights should be taken into consideration in order to achieve justice and equality. The concept of environmental ethics places an emphasis on the responsible use of natural resources and the entitlement of future generations to reside in a world that is rich in environmental health. It is the responsibility of politics to formulate policies for the preservation of the environment by embracing the concepts of environmental ethics. However, it is essential to keep in mind that ethics and politics are complementary to one another, despite the fact that the connection between the two may be quite complicated. When formulating public policy, politicians and others in charge of making decisions need to use ethical principles as a compass. Societies are able to be managed in a manner that is more fair, equitable, and respectful of human rights when implemented in this manner. In the realm of public discourse, ethics and politics come together to establish a strong partnership that serves to safeguard and promote valued principles.

[Within The Context of Alin Badiou, The Relationship Between Ethics and Politics](#)

The philosophical stance of Alain Badiou is intricate and multi-dimensional. When it comes to reevaluating the relationship between philosophy and politics, Badiou's philosophy is a tremendous resource. He contends that in order to develop an alternative political agenda, it is necessary to relinquish the notion of the problem as a crucial intellectual argument. This is a political imperative. When it comes to what Badiou refers to as "the situation," his way of

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thinking places an emphasis on the spatiality of the event as well as the embodiment of the politics of counting. According to Dewsbury (2007), this places his philosophy within the context of geography's concerns with the ethics of anti-foundationalist thought and the manifesto of the politics of thinking outside of structural normative.

According to Paccoud (2018), Badiou's theory is characterized by the introduction of a political subject that operates from inside the state. He refers to this political subject as the state revolutionary. This number makes it possible to engage in "episodic" planning, which further confuses the existing contradiction between agreement and dispute in the realm of politics (Paccoud, 2018). According to Paccoud (2018), Badiou's definition of the link between politics and the state provides a fresh viewpoint that may be used to get a better understanding of the function that politics plays in planning, corporate ethics, and other specific domains. In terms of ethics, Badiou's philosophy indicates that ethics can only develop in connection to a final method of truth that is independent of the economic logic of a circumstance. This is the only instance in which ethics may emerge. According to Couch and Spencer (2013), he contends that economic difficulties need to be understood in connection to reality in the fields of love, art, science, and politics. This viewpoint on ethics contradicts the conventional ideas of business ethics, which only impose restrictions on the activities that may be carried out in the economy. It is possible to consider Badiou's approach to ethics to be a strength due to the fact that it offers a distinct and all-encompassing comprehension of the connection that exists between ethics and politics. On the other hand, Badiou's conception of ethics has also been the target of criticism. Others have attacked his ethics for being intolerant, nihilistic, reactionary, and ambiguous (Lennerfors, 2013). While some academics claim that his ethics replace politics and that his work may be understood as a research of morality rather than politics (Voss, 2018), others have questioned his ethics for being intolerant, nihilistic, reactionary, and ambiguous.

In general, the link between politics and ethics in Alain Badiou's philosophy is one that is both complicated and nuanced. Baidou's writings highlight the significance of locating politics within particular geographical and ethical settings, and his philosophy provides a viewpoint on the link between philosophy and politics. His philosophy also sheds light on the relationship between the two. Badiou's theory of the political subject and his approach to ethics, on the other

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hand, give essential knowledge that may be used to understand the role that politics plays in planning, corporate ethics, and other fields. According to Badiou, there is a fundamental fault with the way ethics are understood in today's society, and this problem might be referred to as nihilism. The confluence of these two primary components results in the formation of this nihilism. It is possible to characterize the first component as "surrender to necessity." However, according to Badiou, the concept of necessity in this context refers to the predominance of capital. The primary objective of the supremacy of capital is to gain complete and total control over individuals' lives. Furthermore, the nihilistic aspect of ethics constitutes the second component. This viewpoint is only concerned with the subject of human mortality, concentrating on the constraints that are placed on human existence by the destructive force of capital. This demonstrates that the current notion of ethics is solely concerned with selecting who lives and who dies because of certain circumstances.

In his argument, Badiou contends that the contemporary perspective on ethics, particularly in the context of the reign of capital, is centered on the organization of life and death, and that this circumstance renders ethics nihilistic. Additionally, the logic of capital has an impact on politics and helps construct legislative regimes for its own specific ends. As a result, politics transforms into an instrument that meets the requirements of the economic reference. Despite the fact that politics is capable of addressing these issues, Badiou asserts that it is unable to resolve economic issues. The political system is not capable of comprehending the intricacy of the economy, and it has a tendency to conceal the problems rather than provide answers. Therefore, its ability to find solutions to the issues that mankind is now experiencing is restricted.

In Badiou's ethics, a nihilistic attitude is adopted because of the fact that he says nothing about these issues. Tolerance and human rights are two examples of concepts that demonstrate that they would rather not desire anything at all and would rather want nothing at all. As a result of this, Badiou contends that ethics, which seeks to appease individuals via the implementation of ideas such as human rights and other similar notions, serves to bolster nihilism rather than to solve actual issues.

In the World, Alain Badiou Presents

Let's take a quick look at some of the significant works that Alain Badiou has produced, which are discussed in this article titled "The Relationship Between Politics and Ethics." His writings, which have had a significant effect on the field of philosophy and which discuss the connection between politics and ethics, have earned Badiou a considerable deal of recognition. The essay that he authored and published in 1989 under the title "Ethics: An Essay on Realism" discusses ethics as a process that is based on universal truth and investigates how ethical activities might be used to fulfill human freedom. In his research "Politics: The Philosophy of Politics," which was published in 1985, he explores the philosophical underpinnings of politics, as well as the formation of the political subject, and he also tackles concerns about the relationship between politics and ethics.

Badiou's philosophical theory is grounded on his research "Philosophy of Event" (1988), in which the idea of event emerges as a vital factor in comprehending the link between politics and ethics. In his research "Ethics: Twenty Lessons" (2001), he takes a comprehensive look at the topic of ethics and explains, from a philosophical point of view, how individuals might participate in behaviors that are ethical. On the other hand, his research "An Infinite Plan: Philosophical, Political, and Artistic Impressions" (published in 1997) places an emphasis on the political and ethical aspects of art and investigates the relationships that occur in these areas. In conclusion, his work titled "Unity and Infinity: A Love Story" (2018) examines the political and ethical aspects of love, as well as the ways in which love is connected to human relationships, social bonds, and freedom. These writings by Alain Badiou are a significant resource for anyone who are interested in comprehending the intricate link that exists between ethics and politics.

Five. Located in Turkey, Alain Badiou

The ideas that Alain Badiou has on the connection between politics and ethics have also garnered a lot of interest in Turkey, and they have been the focus of a number of different

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studies. Researchers, particularly those working in the domains of philosophy, political science, and ethics, have taken Badiou's philosophy to Turkey and addressed it in a context that is specific to the country.

In the year 2020, Hidiroğlu wrote an essay that is considered to be one of the significant studies undertaken in Turkey on the link between politics and ethics as it pertains to Alain Badiou. The idea that Badiou explains the connection between ethics and politics by means of the notion of "reality" is underlined in this article. It is also emphasized that politics has the ability to alter the social order, but that this change must be consistent with ethical ideals. In academic circles in Turkey, there are a number of theses that focus on Badiou's works and philosophy. Additionally, seminars, conferences, and workshops have been hosted on the topic of Alain Badiou's link between politics and ethics. In the course of these events, Badiou's ideas about the connection between politics and ethics have been dissected in great depth. Research on ethical leadership, corporate ethics, and other related fields has also been affected by Badiou's philosophy and has adopted his ideas as a reference. This is in addition to the studies that have been conducted on the link between politics and ethics in Turkey, which have been conducted by Alain Badiou. By drawing connections between Badiou's theoretical framework and contemporary problems in Turkey, these studies demonstrate how philosophical thinking may be applied in the context of the local environment.

Final Thoughts

Through the lens of Alain Badiou's philosophical theory, this research investigated the connection between politics and ethics, with a particular focus on the uniqueness of this connection. Badiou contends that politics and ethics cannot be seen in isolation from one another, and that these two ideas are related to one another and complement one another. According to Badiou, politics has the ability to alter the social order; yet, in order for this change to be successful, it must be consistent with different ethical principles. In this manner, the objective of politics is determined to be the protection of the welfare and justice of the community. In order for individuals to attain genuine equality, justice, freedom, and happiness,

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this approach makes it abundantly evident that politics and ethics are inextricably linked to one another.

There are a number of significant repercussions that result from Badiou's philosophical standpoint. The first thing that he does is demonstrate that the purpose of politics has the capacity to alter and reshape the existing social order. It is highlighted, however, that this development must be consistent with ethical ideals in order to be possible. This demonstrates that politics is not just a method of power struggle or the maintenance of the status quo; rather, it also acts with the intention of ensuring the well-being and fairness of society. The primary emphasis of Badiou's attacks is on the contemporary conception of ethics. One of his arguments is that universal definitions of the notion of ethics might become an "ethical ideology" if they fail to take into account the fact that different circumstances are unique. The fact that this is the case demonstrates that, in addition to adhering to broad standards, ethics necessitates taking into consideration the particulars of the situation.

Conclusion

Another significant aspect of this research is Badiou's ontological approach, which is a significant component. Additionally, he pushes for thinking that does not reduce existence to "one" and recognizes mathematics as a kind of ontology. By doing so, philosophical thinking is separated from the realms of the mystical, religious, and opinion-based thoughts, and it is opened up to an unlimited field of thought. The argument that he makes is that there are several facts, and that each truth starts with their being an event. By demonstrating a commitment to this occurrence, the subject demonstrates that it is a participant in the truth-finding process. The conceptual framework that Badiou has developed demonstrates that ethics and politics are inseparable parts of the same whole, and that the only way to achieve freeing politics is to do it in line with ethical principles. In this particular setting, the notion of the subject is also of tremendous significance. This is due to the fact that the subject acknowledges the indeterminate and demonstrates allegiance to it, which is what kickstarts the process of discovering the truth.

The ideas that Badiou suggests help to a more profound comprehension of politics and ethics by providing a fresh viewpoint on the modern societal issues that are being faced.

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